

RESEARCH

Open Access

“Is a general belief in one’s capabilities related to mental and physical health?”: The relationships between self-efficacy, health outcomes, and health-related behaviour

Lucie Horelicova^{1,2}

Abstract

Background Self-efficacy, reflecting an individual’s belief in their ability to achieve goals, influences motivation, behaviour, and success. Understanding the interrelationships between general self-efficacy (GSE) and chronic conditions can contribute to developing prevention and treatment strategies.

Methods We surveyed 3,532 participants (age = 31.73 ± 13.13 years, 66% females) using an online questionnaire that assessed GSE, chronic conditions, health complaints, and health-related behaviours. Binary logistic regression analysed associations.

Results Higher GSE levels were associated with reduced odds of several chronic conditions, including pain of unclear origin (4%, 95% CI [0–8], $p < 0.05$), anxiety (6%, 95% CI [4–9], $p < 0.001$), and depression (5%, 95% CI [2–8], $p < 0.01$). Furthermore, higher GSE levels were associated with a 10% (95% CI [9, 12], $p < 0.001$) reduction in the odds of nervousness, an 8% (95% CI [6–10], $p < 0.001$) reduction in the odds of heart pounding/chest pain, and a 7% reduction in the odds of depressive feelings (95% CI [6–8], $p < 0.001$) and irritability/bad mood (95% CI [6–9], $p < 0.001$). Overall, negative associations were found with all tested health complaints except for intestinal complaints. Conversely, higher GSE levels were associated with increased odds of asthma (3%, 95% CI [0–5], $p < 0.05$) and coffee consumption (2%, 95% CI [1–4], $p < 0.001$).

Conclusion GSE was moderately associated with health complaints, chronic conditions, and health-related behaviours, suggesting its importance in the prevention and management of chronic diseases.

Keywords Self-efficacy, Chronic conditions, Health complaints, Health-related behaviour, Risk factors

*Correspondence:

Lukas Novak

l.j.novak@umcg.nl

¹OUSHI - Olomouc University Social Health Institute, Palacký University
Olomouc, Univerzitní 244/22, Olomouc 771 11, Czech Republic

²Department of Community and Occupational Medicine, University
Medical Center Groningen, University of Groningen, Groningen, The
Netherlands

© The Author(s) 2026. **Open Access** This article is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License, which permits use, sharing, adaptation, distribution and reproduction in any medium or format, as long as you give appropriate credit to the original author(s) and the source, provide a link to the Creative Commons licence, and indicate if changes were made. The images or other third party material in this article are included in the article’s Creative Commons licence, unless indicated otherwise in a credit line to the material. If material is not included in the article’s Creative Commons licence and your intended use is not permitted by statutory regulation or exceeds the permitted use, you will need to obtain permission directly from the copyright holder. To view a copy of this licence, visit <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>.

Background

Chronic conditions represent a major global threat to human health. Their pervasive and long-lasting nature necessitates urgent and sustained action from the global health community. Consequently, scientific and medical researchers remain strongly committed to investigating the aetiology of these conditions, identifying effective preventive strategies, and developing evidence-based pharmacological and therapeutic interventions [1, 2]. The onset, prevention, and treatment of chronic conditions are shaped by a wide range of determinants [3]. Many of these factors have been extensively studied, including alcohol consumption [4, 5], smoking [6, 7], physical activity [8–10], and diet [11–13]. However, several important determinants remain insufficiently explored. In recent years, growing attention has been directed toward the influence of mental health, well-being, and psychological characteristics on overall health outcomes [14–17]. One such under-examined determinant that may relate to mental health, psychological well-being, personality traits, and numerous other health-related variables is general self-efficacy (GSE) [18, 19].

Self-efficacy (SE) is an individual's belief in their ability to achieve goals, which influences their motivation, behaviour, effort, persistence, intensity of negative emotions, level of achievement, and social environment [20, 21]. It refers to the control over events, the ability to influence one's life, and to adapt to the situation [21, 22]. According to Bandura [21], SE is associated with certain human activities. This specific self-efficacy (SSE) is now studied in various areas of human activity, including education [23], reading [24], smoking [25], entrepreneurship [26], and social networks [27]. In contrast, Schwarzer [28] describes SE as a situation-independent and relatively enduring characteristic of a person that can serve as a dispositional resource in times of stress, incorporating all previous successes and failures. Such SE is called general self-efficacy and represents a global sense of personal capability perceived across situations and tasks [28, 29].

SE is a psychological characteristic that has the potential to influence health [30], according to the holistic bio-psycho-social model. Research has shown significant links between higher levels of SE and reduced symptoms of mental illness, as well as better management and adherence to treatment [31, 32]. Recent findings, for instance, indicate that higher SE predicts fewer daily anxiety symptoms and faster early treatment response in anxiety disorders [33]. Furthermore, higher levels of SE are consistently correlated with lower stress levels [34], which is important because chronic stress significantly contributes to the development and worsening of many mental illnesses. Conversely, low levels of SE are associated with higher levels of anxiety, depression [35, 36],

stress [36, 37] and fear [38]. Some studies suggest existing relationships between SE and certain somatic chronic conditions, such as cancer [39–41], diabetes [42], hypertension [43], and asthma [44, 45].

Chronic conditions are a global problem. According to WHO [1, 46], chronic diseases kill 17 million people under the age of 70 each year, out of a total of 41 million deaths. These long-term conditions arise from environmental, socioeconomic, behavioural, biological, and psychological factors [3, 46, 47]. Environmental risk factors include, for example, air pollution, weather changes, and UV radiation [3, 48, 49]. Socioeconomic risk factors, for example, include income, age, gender, and ethnicity [3, 50]. Behavioural risk factors are, for example, smoking, excessive drinking, drug abuse [51], unhealthy eating habits [52, 53], and physical inactivity [54]. Biological risk factors include, for example, elevated arterial pressure [55] and genetic predisposition [56–58]. Psychological risk factors are most commonly represented in the literature by stress and neuroticism [59–62].

Examining the aforementioned risk factors for chronic conditions and the areas where SE can impact health, we observe interesting intersections. According to the available studies, the level of SE is associated with health-risk behaviours, such as smoking, drinking alcohol [51], quality of dietary habits [52], and amount of physical activity [54]. These behaviours are also among the main risk factors for chronic conditions [3]. From this perspective, the degree of SE is linked with some risk factors for the development of chronic conditions and could, therefore, impact their origin.

To the best of our knowledge, most published studies examine chronic conditions and health complaints in the context of SSE, not GSE. These studies typically examine the relationship between SE and chronic conditions, or the management of health complaints. A similar situation applies to the relationship between SE and health-related behaviour, with much evidence associated with SSE. We did not find studies directly addressing the link between health-related behaviour and GSE. However, identifying the associations between GSE, chronic conditions, health complaints, and health-related behaviours could influence the view on the prevention and treatment of chronic conditions and thus contribute to reducing their prevalence and mortality. Thus, our study aims to explore the relationship between GSE, selected chronic conditions, health complaints, and health-related behaviour.

Methods

Participants

Data were collected through an online questionnaire hosted on a platform developed by the Olomouc University Social and Health Institute (OUSHI). Our sample consisted of adult participants who volunteered to take

part in the survey. Participation was conditional upon signing an informed consent form before beginning the survey. The study received ethical approval from the Faculty of Theology Ethics Committee of Palacký University in Olomouc (No. 2020/4).

Data collection was conducted between September 2022 and January 2024 using a snowball sampling method facilitated by university students. The data gathering process was incorporated into university coursework, with student participation serving the dual purpose of earning academic credits and fulfilling a core component of their educational learning objective. Students served as the initial contacts, tasked with reaching out to 10 participants from their immediate and wider social circles, motivating them to complete the questionnaire, and subsequently encouraging its further dissemination among their contacts. Of the 7,253 respondents who agreed to participate in the survey and completed basic socio-demographic data, 1,333 were excluded due to the high likelihood of having completed the questionnaire multiple times. This likelihood was calculated using the formula:

$$p = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n x_{ji} \neq 0}{n}$$

In the equation, p represents the probability of browser type and version matching for each student, x_{ji} denotes the number of rows where the i -th element from the interviewer's code column matches the j -th element from the browser's type and version row used to complete the questionnaire, and n refers to the total number of rows in the matrix. Subsequently, a tolerance limit was calculated using these match probabilities. In the equation below, m represents the number of questionnaires the student completes, and q is the student's designation.

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{more significant tolerance limit} \\ & = p * \text{med}(m_1, m_2, m_3 \dots m_k) * \sum_{q=1}^n (q_m > 1) \end{aligned}$$

Then, the responses of 2,098 people who completed the questionnaire in under 26 min were excluded, as this was the shortest amount of time deemed necessary to complete the questionnaire truthfully. Respondents were repeatedly asked about their weight, age and height. If their answers to the same question differed by more than 2 kg, years or cm, they were excluded ($n=380$). Participants who provided identical answers to at least three distinct questionnaires forming part of the comprehensive test battery were also excluded ($n=207$). The final sample size, therefore, consisted of 3,532 participants aged 18 to 80 ($M=31.73$, $SD=13.13$; females: 66%).

Measures

Self-efficacy was measured by the Generalized Self-Efficacy Scale (GSES) [63]. The GSES consists of ten items designed to assess an individual's perceived self-efficacy, that is, their belief in their ability to face new or challenging situations and overcome related obstacles and setbacks. For example: "It is easy for me to stick to my aims and accomplish my goals." [63]. For each item, respondents can choose from four options ranging from not at all true [1] to exactly true [4]. The higher the total score, the greater the individual's generalized sense of self-efficacy. The Czech version of GSES was used in this study [64]. Cronbach's alpha was 0.88 for our sample. The GSES was used as a continuous variable in the research.

Health-related behaviour was assessed using the question: 'How often in the past month have you smoked/drank alcohol/used illegal drugs/drank coffee/used the TV or computer to relax?' Respondents selected from the following six options: never (1), about once or twice (2), about every week (3), more than once a week (4), every day (5), or many times a day (6). For analysis, responses for each item were dichotomized. The occurrence of alcohol consumption, smoking, and illegal drug use was defined by responses 2–6. The occurrence of coffee consumption and the use of TV or a computer to relax was defined by responses 5 and 6.

The prevalence of physical chronic conditions was assessed by the question, 'Do you have a diagnosed long-term physical illness or disability?' followed by a multiple-choice list of selected chronic conditions (allergies, arthritis, back pain, migraine, thyroid disease, ischemic heart disease, hypertension, diabetes, pelvic pain, chronic tiredness, psoriasis, obesity, skin diseases, asthma, cancer, gastric reflux, pain unclear origin, inflammatory bowel disease, chronic lung disease, stomach or duodenal ulcers, stroke, none of these conditions). The occurrence of a physical chronic condition was indicated by the respondent selecting it from the list.

The presence of psychiatric chronic conditions was measured by the question, "Do you have a diagnosed long-term psychiatric illness or disorder?" followed by a multiple-choice list of selected conditions (ADHD, paranoia, depression, paranoid schizophrenia, schizotypal disorder, anxiety), with occurrence indicated by the respondents' selection. The included conditions were considered suitable because their symptom profiles and treatment requirements remain relatively stable over time and are not characterised by distinct episodic changes [65–69].

The frequency of health complaints (headache, stomachache, back pain, intestinal complaints, feelings of depression, irritability/bad mood, nervousness, trouble falling asleep, dizziness, sore throat/cold, heart pounding/chest pain, tingling in limbs or face) was assessed by

a question 'In the past month, how often have you had the following issues?' Respondents then chose from the following answers: never (1), about once or twice (2), about every week (3), more than once a week (4), or every day (5). For further analysis, responses for each item were dichotomised, with categories 3–5 pooled and treated as indicating the presence of the complaint.

Socio-demographic data were collected, including age, gender, education, and economic status. Age, gender, and education served as covariates in the subsequent analyses, while economic status was included for descriptive purposes only. Education was assessed using seven categorical levels, ranging from Basic school to Postgraduate – Doctorate. The specific response categories were: Basic school, Secondary vocational school, High school, Higher vocational school, Undergraduate (bachelor's degree), Postgraduate – Master's (M.A., M.Sc., M.Phil.), and Postgraduate – Doctorate (PhD, D.Phil., D.Sc.). Economic status was measured using the following nominal categories: student, employed, freelancer, unemployed, or retired/invalid pensioner. Gender was reported dichotomously (female or male), and age was recorded as a continuous numerical variable.

Statistical analysis

In the first step, we tested the socio-demographic differences in the degree of GSE. The Shapiro-Wilk test revealed that our data did not meet the normality assumption; therefore, non-parametric methods were used for further analysis. The differences among the groups were tested using a Kruskal-Wallis test. If the result was statistically significant, a Wilcoxon test was performed for gender comparisons, and a Dunn's test was performed for comparisons of education and economic status.

We used binary logistic regression to analyse the associations between GSE (independent variable) and all binomial dependent variables. During the first step, we analysed the relationship between the selected psychological and physical chronic conditions and the GSE. Further, we dichotomized the variables of health complaints (headache, stomachache, back pain, intestinal complaints, feelings of depression, irritability/bad mood, nervousness, trouble falling asleep, dizziness, sore throat/cold, heart pounding/chest pain, tingling in limbs or face) and health-related behaviours (smoking, drinking alcohol, using illegal drugs, drinking coffee, using the TV or computer to relax). Subsequently, we examined the relationships between health complaints and GSE, as well as between health-related behaviours and GSE, using binary logistic regression.

In all analyses, we adjusted for age, gender, and education. Non-adjusted results were also reported. Correction for multiple testing was performed using the

Benjamini-Hochberg correction. Data were analysed using IBM SPSS Statistics for Windows, Version 21.0 (IBM Corp., Armonk, NY, USA) and the Psychtoolbox toolkit [70].

Results

Description of the socio-demographic characteristics of the research sample and testing sociodemographic differences in GSE

The most significant proportion of our sample was represented by employed people and individuals with a high school education. The highest GSE scores were achieved by men, freelancers, and people with a master's degree. The socio-demographic characteristics of the research sample and the differences between selected sociodemographic factors in GSE are described in more detail in Table 1.

GSE and chronic conditions

The results of the binary logistic regression for physical chronic conditions indicated that higher levels of GSE were associated with a 4% decrease in the odds of having pain of unclear origin and a 3% increase in the odds of having asthma; no significant associations were found in other cases.

The results of the binary logistic regression for psychiatric chronic conditions indicated that higher GSE levels were associated with a 6% reduction in the odds of having anxiety and a 5% reduction in the odds of having depression. No significant associations were found for other psychiatric chronic conditions. The results are described in more detail in Table 2.

GSE and health complaints

There was a significant negative link between GSE and all health complaints examined. After adjusting for age, gender, and education, the significance of intestinal complaints was no longer evident. The strongest association was found between GSE and nervousness (OR=0.90, $p<0.001$). The weakest relationship was between GSE and tingling in limbs or face (OR=0.97, $p<0.05$). Table 3 provides more detailed results.

GSE and health-related behaviour

Binary logistic regression indicated that higher GSE levels were associated with a 3% increase in the odds of coffee consumption. No relationship was found between GSE and the use of illegal drugs, nor was one found between GSE and smoking. Furthermore, no significant associations were found between GSE and alcohol drinking, or between GSE and using a TV or computer to relax. More detailed results are described in Table 4.

Table 1 Descriptive statistics of the study sample and Socio-Demographic comparison

Variable	n (%)	GSE Group difference	GSE M(SD)
Gender			
1. Man	1200 (34.0)	$p < 0.001$	29.6 (5.2)
2. Woman	2332 (66.0)		27.8 (4.9)
Economic status			
1. Student	1282 (36.3)	$p < 0.001$ (1–3***, 1–4***, 2–4**, 3–4***, 4–5***)	27.7 (5.1)
2. Retired or invalid pensioner	114 (3.2)		28.3 (5.3)
3. Employed	1744 (49.4)		28.6 (5.0)
4. Freelancer	268 (7.6)		30.5 (4.9)
5. Unemployed	124 (3.5)		27.6 (5.4)
Education			
1. Basic School	188 (5.3)	$p < 0.001$ (1–3*, 1–5***, 1–6***, 2–6***, 3–6***, 4–6***, 5–6*)	26.6 (5.7)
2. Secondary vocational school	338 (9.6)		28.1 (5.2)
3. High school	1830 (51.8)		28.2 (5.0)
4. Higher vocational school	137 (3.9)		27.3 (4.4)
5. Undergraduate (bachelor's degree)	470 (13.3)		28.71 (5.0)
6. Postgraduate - master	535 (15.2)		29.9 (4.9)
7. Postgraduate - doctorate	34 (1.0)		29.5 (4.3)

GSE General Self-efficacy; M Mean; SD Standard Deviation

* $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$; *** $p < 0.001$. 1–3 *** and 1–4 *** indicate post-hoc pairwise comparisons between two specific groups within the analysed variable (Economic Status, Education), accompanied by an interpretation of statistical significance. The numbers correspond to the group categories (e.g., 1 vs. 3, 1 vs. 4), and this interpretation applies to all other comparisons listed

Discussion

Our research aimed to assess the relationships between GSE and chronic conditions, health complaints, and health-related behaviours. The results showed that higher levels of GSE are associated with a reduction in the odds of having pain of unclear origin, depression, and anxiety, but also with an increase in the odds of having asthma. There was also a negative association between GSE and the health complaints studied. The only exception was intestinal complaints, for which statistical significance diminished after adjustment for age, gender, and education. Regarding health-related behaviour, only one significant relationship emerged, indicating that higher GSE was associated with increased odds of coffee consumption.

Our finding that GSE was negatively associated with pain of unclear origin is consistent with research by Petersen et al. [71], which describes existing relationships between GSE and the prevalence of functional somatic disorders. This research includes findings that higher levels of GSE reduce pain, as well as functional impairment. A similar relationship was also found by Wojeck et al. [72] in a study of patients with systemic sclerosis. According to a study by Tsuji et al. [73], higher levels of pain self-efficacy correlate with lower levels of pain-related disability, anxiety, and depression and, in the context of the fear-avoidance model, may serve as a protective factor against the vicious cycle of chronic pain. Pain self-efficacy in the aforementioned study represents a component of the fear-avoidance model that influences our response to pain [74–76]. Based on our findings, GSE could work similarly. The experience of stressful situations is one of four factors that determine adaptive or non-adaptive response strategies to pain [74]. Mastery of a stressful situation is typically associated with a reduction in stress and psychological problems, and it has also been linked to an increase in GSE [77, 78]. In turn, GSE is often suggested to be beneficial for improving adaptive coping strategies and mitigating stress [79, 80]. Thus, GSE could promote an adaptive response to pain, thereby decreasing the risk of chronic pain. For some chronic pain, the cause is not clear. Such pain may be psychosomatic in origin and, therefore, strongly influenced by stress and psychological state [81, 82]. By its positive effect on stress management, GSE may also contribute to reducing the incidence of this type of pain.

Our research has also shown a positive relationship between GSE and asthma. We found no studies examining the association between the development of asthma and GSE. However, some studies confirmed the relationship between SSE and asthma treatment and management [44, 45, 83–85]. Studies have shown that a significant trigger for asthma is primarily harmful air pollution, environmental allergens, and viruses [60–62], as well as high physical activity [86–88]. Higher levels of SE may contribute to increased physical activity and a more active lifestyle [66–70], which in turn could increase exposure to certain types of triggers [89].

Our results showed a negative relationship between GSE and anxiety and depression. Other studies also confirm that higher levels of SE are associated with a lower likelihood of depression and anxiety [36, 90–92]. Given that depression and anxiety, as psychological illnesses, are by their very nature primarily caused by psychological factors [93–97], the association of GSE with their presence is conceptually sound. The development of anxiety is closely related to stressful, traumatic, and otherwise challenging life situations, as well as interpersonal relationships and childhood shyness and nervousness,

Table 2 Binary logistic regression results of GSE and physical and psychiatric chronic conditions

Variable	Effect type		Allergies	Arthritis	Back pain	Migraine	Thyroid disease	Ischemic heart disease
GSE	crude	OR	1.00	1.02	0.99	1.00	0.98	0.98
		95% CI	(0.99–1.02)	(0.98–1.06)	(0.97–1.01)	(0.97–1.02)	(0.95–1.01)	(0.91–1.04)
GSE	adjusted	OR	0.99	1.01	0.99	1.01	0.98	0.96
		95% CI	(0.98–1.01)	(0.96–1.06)	(0.97–1.01)	(0.98–1.04)	(0.96–1.01)	(0.89–1.03)
Variable	Effect type		Diabetes	Pelvic pain	Chronic tiredness	Psoriasis	Obesity	Skin diseases
GSE	crude	OR	1.00	0.98	0.97	1.02	1.01	1.01
		95% CI	(0.95–1.04)	(0.95–1.01)	(0.93–1.02)	(0.96–1.09)	(0.99–1.04)	(0.99–1.04)
GSE	adjusted	OR	0.99	1.01	0.98	1.02	1.00	1.02
		95% CI	(0.94–1.04)	(0.98–1.04)	(0.93–1.02)	(0.96–1.09)	(0.97–1.03)	(0.99–1.04)
Variable	Effect type		Cancer	Gastric reflux	Pain of unclear origin	Inflammatory bowel disease	Chronic lung disease	Stomach or duodenal ulcers
GSE	crude	OR	1.01	1.00	0.96 *	1.03	1.00	0.95
		95% CI	(0.94–1.09)	(0.97–1.04)	(0.92–0.99)	(0.97–1.1)	(0.92–1.08)	(0.88–1.02)
GSE	adjusted	OR	1.02	1.00	0.96 *	1.03	1.00	0.95
		95% CI	(0.94–1.1)	(0.96–1.03)	(0.92–1.00)	(0.97–1.09)	(0.92–1.08)	(0.88–1.03)
Variable	Effect type		Asthma	Stroke	Hypertension			
GSE	crude	OR	1.01	0.99	1.01			
		95% CI	(0.99–1.04)	(0.86–1.15)	(0.99–1.04)			
GSE	adjusted	OR	1.03 *	0.93	0.99			
		95% CI	(1.00–1.05)	(0.78–1.11)	(0.96–1.02)			
Variable	Effect type		Paranoia	Depression	Schizotypal disorder	Paranoid schizophrenia	Anxiety	ADHD
GSE	crude	OR	0.92	0.94 ***	0.91	0.96	0.92 ***	0.98
		95% CI	(0.81–1.04)	(0.91–0.97)	(0.83–1.01)	(0.84–1.1)	(0.9–0.95)	(0.94–1.02)
GSE	adjusted	OR	0.95	0.95 **	0.93	0.97	0.94 ***	0.99
		95% CI	(0.84–1.07)	(0.92–0.98)	(0.84–1.02)	(0.85–1.11)	(0.91–0.96)	(0.95–1.03)

N = 3, 532; Online Survey; Covariates = age, gender, education

GSE General Self-Efficacy; OR Odds Ratio

95% CI – 95% Confidence Interval

* $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$; *** $p < 0.001$

Table 3 Binary logistic regression results of GSE and health complaints

Variable	Effect type		Headache	Stomachache	Back pain	Intestinal complaints
GSE	crude	OR	0.95 ***	0.95 ***	0.97 ***	0.97 ***
		95% CI	(0.93–0.96)	(0.93–0.96)	(0.95–0.98)	(0.95–0.99)
GSE	adjusted	OR	0.96 ***	0.96 ***	0.98 **	0.98
		95% CI	(0.95–0.98)	(0.94–0.98)	(0.96–0.99)	(0.96–1.00)
Variable	Effect type		Nervousness	Trouble falling asleep	Dizziness	Sore throat/cold
GSE	crude	OR	0.89 ***	0.96 ***	0.93 ***	0.96 ***
		95% CI	(0.88–0.91)	(0.94–0.97)	(0.91–0.95)	(0.94–0.98)
GSE	adjusted	OR	0.90 ***	0.96 ***	0.94 ***	0.97 **
		95% CI	(0.88–0.91)	(0.95–0.98)	(0.92–0.97)	(0.95–0.99)
Variable	Effect type		Feelings of depression	Irritability/ bad mood	Heart pounding/ chest pain	Tingling in limbs or face
GSE	crude	OR	0.92 ***	0.92 ***	0.91 ***	0.97 **
		95% CI	(0.90–0.93)	(0.91–0.93)	(0.89–0.93)	(0.95–0.99)
GSE	adjusted	OR	0.93 ***	0.93 ***	0.92 ***	0.97 *
		95% CI	(0.92–0.94)	(0.91–0.94)	(0.90–0.94)	(0.95–0.99)

N = 3, 532; Online Survey; Covariates = age, gender, education

GSE General Self-Efficacy; OR Odds Ratio

95% CI – 95% Confidence Interval

* $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$; *** $p < 0.001$

Table 4 Binary logistic regression results of GSE and Health-Related behaviour

Variable	Effect type	Smoking	Drinking alcohol	Using illegal drugs
GSE	crude OR (95% CI)	0.99 (0.98–1.01)	0.99 (0.98–1.01)	1.01 (0.99–1.03)
GSE	adjusted OR (95% CI)	0.98 (0.98–1.01)	0.99 (0.97–1.01)	1.01 (0.98–1.03)
Variable	Effect type	Drinking coffee	Using TV or a PC to relax	
GSE	crude OR (95% CI)	1.03 (1.02–1.05) ***	0.99 (0.98–1.01)	
GSE	adjusted OR (95% CI)	1.03 (1.01–1.04) ***	0.99 (0.97–1.00)	

N = 3, 532; Online Survey; Covariates = age, gender, education

GSE General Self-Efficacy; OR Odds Ratio

95% CI – 95% Confidence Interval

* $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$; *** $p < 0.001$

among other factors [98–102]. The social environment and interpersonal relationships also play an essential role in building SE [21, 22, 103]. Good relationships, healthy self-esteem, and individuality are linked with higher SE and resilience to harmful environmental influences and stressful situations [104, 105]. SE and resilience may promote better coping with stressful situations, thereby protecting against anxiety [36, 104, 106]. The association between higher levels of SE and a lower occurrence of anxiety and depression has been established in numerous studies [107–110]. Conversely, there are studies that suggest a link between the presence of anxiety, depression, and lower levels of SE [101, 102]. These findings indicate that it would be beneficial to focus on increasing SE in the therapies of individuals with depression and anxiety.

All health complaints examined, except intestinal complaints, were negatively associated with GSE, with the strongest relationship observed for nervousness. Other studies have already suggested a link between, for example, SE and back pain [111], headache [112], dizziness [113], mood disorders [95], and sleep disturbances [114], which is consistent with our results. Many health complaints are influenced by an unhealthy diet [115, 116], lack of exercise [117, 118], stress [119], and an overall unhealthy lifestyle [120]. The improvement of many of these health factors is associated with higher levels of SE [121–124]. Similarly, higher SE is linked to a reduction in stress and an improvement in overall well-being [109, 110, 125], which, in line with the psychosomatic approach, are considered important health factors [81, 82, 126]. Therefore, in relation to health complaints, GSE may have a positive impact on crucial behavioural and psychological determinants of health. Concurrently, it is necessary to note that a wide range of health complaints,

such as stress, may be associated with lower levels of SE [127, 128]. These findings suggest that both the prevention and management of health complaints should include components focused on enhancing SE and psychological well-being.

Our results further showed a positive association between GSE and coffee consumption. We found no studies that specifically investigated this association. However, we did find research presenting the positive effects of coffee consumption on reducing stress, symptoms of depression and anxiety, and on improving health and well-being [129–132]. These relationships may contribute to explaining the association between GSE and coffee consumption. Stress, significant mental effort, and work pressure, which can lead to psychological problems, are often associated with demanding job positions frequently held by highly educated individuals [133]. These individuals not only have higher levels of GSE but also consume more coffee, according to research [134]. Caffeine in coffee can help reduce fatigue and improve concentration, in addition to other positive effects on physical and mental state [129, 135]. The positive relationship between GSE and coffee consumption can therefore be explained as a strategy for coping with high workload and fatigue.

Strengths and limitations

The primary strength of our research is the sample size. A further contribution is that, unlike most previous studies that focus on various specific self-efficacies, we investigate the relationship between GSE and chronic conditions and health problems. We view GSE as a personality trait that may function as a psychological risk factor and play a role in the occurrence of health problems. Our research demonstrates that even lesser-known psychological factors, which are susceptible to influence, can play a protective role in maintaining health.

A significant weakness of our research is the method used for data collection. The use of a snowball sampling approach meant that a random selection of participants could not be ensured. Consequently, this design introduced a potential for selection bias and may have resulted in a sample that was not fully representative of the target population. This limitation is further exacerbated by the sample's composition, which predominantly consists of students and employed individuals rather than those from other economic statuses. Therefore, the generalizability of our findings is constrained to the studied sample, meaning the results should be interpreted with caution when applied to a broader population.

A further limitation is the possibility of duplicate questionnaire completion. This arises from the recruitment method involving students during their practical training, increasing the likelihood that some participants were approached multiple times. To mitigate this issue, we

utilized methods to detect duplicated responses in our data. We also acknowledge the reliance on self-reported data concerning health complaints. This method carries the risk of biases, notably social desirability bias or recall bias. Moreover, the respondents' current psychological state may subtly influence their subjective assessment of both their own health and their self-efficacy. This suggests a potential for the observed associations to be somewhat exaggerated, which should be considered when interpreting the results. Finally, our research may have been influenced by the fact that multiple risk factors contribute to the occurrence of chronic conditions, which can be challenging to capture in data collection. While genetic predispositions play a crucial role in many chronic conditions, most of the conditions we studied were not primarily caused by genetics. This factor helped to reduce the risk of bias in our results. For instance, chronic lung diseases (including cystic fibrosis), which are mainly caused by a genetic mutation, showed no statistically significant association with GSE in our study.

Implications for practice

The results of our research can raise awareness of the importance of GSE for physical and mental health. Our findings may also highlight the role of lesser-known psychological risk factors in the prevention and management of chronic conditions and their associated symptoms.

Implications for research

Our research findings point to existing relationships between GSE, multiple chronic conditions, several health complaints associated with chronic diseases, and health-related behaviours. A closer understanding of their interrelationships would be aided by qualitative research focusing, for example, on the construction of GSE, the extent of GSE, and possible changes in people with chronic conditions. More precise insights into the development of relationships between GSE and chronic conditions could then be provided by a longitudinal study.

The associations between GSE and health complaints indicate that, alongside SSE, GSE may also potentially improve the prevention and management of chronic conditions and health problems. Further research could investigate whether, for some diseases, health complaints, behaviours and areas of human activity, the relationships found for SSE also apply to GSE. The results could help to understand the nature of the concept of self-efficacy and whether it relates to a specific situation or whether it is a personality trait that influences behaviour and thinking in general.

Conclusion

Our results indicate that higher levels of GSE are associated with reduced odds of several health complaints, including anxiety, depression, and nervousness, and with favourable patterns of health-related behaviours. While GSE was significantly associated with only a limited number of chronic conditions, the observed relationships with health complaints and health-related behaviours suggest that GSE may serve as a broader psychological resource relevant to the onset, course, and day-to-day management of chronic conditions. Many of the health complaints examined also represent common symptoms of chronic diseases, which implies that higher GSE may help alleviate certain symptom manifestations and thereby contribute to improved psychological well-being. Improved psychological well-being, in turn, may facilitate more effective self-management of chronic conditions.

Most existing evidence linking self-efficacy to chronic conditions focuses on specific self-efficacy. However, our findings suggest that general self-efficacy may play a similar role at a broader, non-condition-specific level. Although GSE does not replace SSE in explaining disease-specific behaviours, the associations we identified indicate that GSE may constitute an overarching psychological factor that co-occurs with and potentially supports processes involved in symptom management and certain forms of adaptive health-related behaviours.

Abbreviations

ADHD	Attention-deficit/Hyperactivity disorder
GSE	General Self-Efficacy
GSES	General Self-Efficacy Scale
OR	Odds Ratio
OUSHI	Olomouc University Social Health Institute
PC	Personal Computer
SE	Self-Efficacy
SSE	Specific Self-Efficacy
TV	Television
WHO	World Health Organization
95% CI	95% Confidence Interval

Supplementary Information

The online version contains supplementary material available at <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40359-026-03996-7>.

Supplementary Material 1.

Acknowledgements

We are grateful to students from the University of Hradec Kralove for their help in data collection. The names of students who helped with the collection of data can be found here: <https://osf.io/c7nzg>.

Authors' contributions

Conceptualization, L.H., L.N., K.M.; methodology, L.H., L.N., K.M.; validation, L.H.; formal analysis, L.H.; investigation, L.H.; resources, P.T., K.M.; data curation, L.N., K.M.; writing—original draft preparation, L.H.; writing—review and editing, L.N., K.M., P.T., R.Z.; supervision, L.N., P.T., K.M., R.Z.; funding acquisition, P.T., K.M.

Funding

The work was supported by the ERDF/ESF project DigiWELL (No. CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004583).

Data availability

Anonymized data, code, and other materials related to this study are available at the Open Science Framework (OSF) website under the following DOI: <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/5RM9X>.

Declarations

Ethics approval and consent to participate

Before joining the study, all participants received information about its objectives, the confidentiality of their data, their freedom to withdraw anytime, and an introduction to the online questionnaire. They were required to sign an informed consent form before their participation. The study received approval from the Ethics Committee at the Social Health Institute of Olomouc University, Palacký University Olomouc, under reference number 2020/04.

Consent for publication

Not applicable.

Competing interests

The authors declare no competing interests.

Received: 28 October 2024 / Accepted: 9 January 2026

Published online: 05 March 2026

References

- WHO. Invisible numbers. 2022. Available from: <https://www.who.int/teams/noncommunicable-diseases/invisible-numbers>. Cited 2023 Nov 7.
- Wang Y, Wang J. Modelling and prediction of global non-communicable diseases. *BMC PUBLIC Health*. 2020;20(1):822.
- Budreviciute A, Damiati S, Sabir DK, Onder K, Schuller-Goetzburg P, Plakys G, et al. Management and prevention strategies for Non-communicable diseases (NCDs) and their risk factors. *Front Public Health*. 2020;8:574111.
- Tian Y, Liu J, Zhao Y, Jiang N, Liu X, Zhao G, et al. Alcohol consumption and all-cause and cause-specific mortality among US adults: prospective cohort study. *BMC Med*. 2023;21(1):208.
- Rehm J, Rovira P, Llamas-Falcón L, Shield KD. Dose–Response relationships between levels of alcohol use and risks of mortality or Disease, for all People, by Age, Sex, and specific risk factors. *Nutrients*. 2021;13(8):2652.
- Kasza KA, O'Connor RJ, Cummings KM, Mahoney MC. Cigarette smoking and chronic disease in the united States, 2021–2023. *Prev Med*. 2025;201:108378.
- Dai X, Gil GF, Reitsma MB, Ahmad NS, Anderson JA, Bisignano C, et al. Health effects associated with smoking: a burden of proof study. *Nat Med*. 2022;28(10):2045–55.
- Boraita RJ, González-García H, Pérez JG, Álvarez-Kurogi L, Córdón JT, López RC, et al. The impact of physical activity levels on mental health and sleep quality in university online students. *J Public Health*. 2025. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10389-025-02559-1>. Cited 2025 Sept 11.
- Jones PAT, Moolyk A, Ruchat SM, Ali MU, Fleming K, Meyer S, et al. Impact of postpartum physical activity on cardiometabolic health, breastfeeding, injury and infant growth and development: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Br J Sports Med*. 2025;59(8):539–49.
- Maddock JE, Frumkin H. Physical activity in natural settings: an opportunity for lifestyle medicine. *Am J Lifestyle Med*. 2025;19(1):73–87.
- Godos J, Guglielmetti M, Ferraris C, Frias-Toral E, Domínguez Azpíroz I, Lipari V, et al. Mediterranean diet and quality of life in adults: a systematic review. *Nutrients*. 2025;17(3):577.
- Kumar S, Mukherjee R, Gaur P, Leal É, Lyu X, Ahmad S, et al. Unveiling roles of beneficial gut bacteria and optimal diets for health. *Front Microbiol*. 2025;16. Available from: <https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/microbiology/articles/10.3389/fmicb.2025.1527755/full>. Cited 2025 Dec 2.
- Clemente-Suárez VJ, Redondo-Flórez L, Martín-Rodríguez A, Curiel-Regueros A, Rubio-Zarapuz A, Tornero-Aguilera JF. Impact of vegan and vegetarian diets on neurological health: a critical review. *Nutrients*. 2025;17(5):884.
- Pizzol D, Trott M, Butler L, Barnett Y, Ford T, Neufeld SA, et al. Relationship between severe mental illness and physical multimorbidity: a meta-analysis and call for action. *BMJ Ment Health*. 2023;26(1):e300870.
- Schaap G, Davelaar JF, ten Klooster PM, Doggen CJM, van der Palen J, Bode C, et al. One-year trajectories of physical and mental health-related quality of life, fatigue and dyspnoea in COVID-19 survivors. *Qual Life Res*. 2025;34(2):341–51.
- Bhatta D, Sizer MA, Acharya B, Banjara D. Assessment of mental and physical health outcomes over time in an integrated care setting. *BMC Prim Care*. 2025;26(1):181.
- Zulkifli MM, Abdul Rahman R, Muhamad R, Abdul Kadir A, Roslan NS, Mustafa N. The lived experience of resilience in chronic disease among adults in Asian countries: a scoping review of qualitative studies. *BMC Psychol*. 2024;12(1):773.
- Bill V, Wilke A, Sonsmann F, Rocholl M. What is the current state of research concerning self-efficacy in exercise behaviour? Protocol for two systematic evidence maps. *BMJ Open*. 2023;13(8):e070359.
- Warner LM, Schwarzer R. Self-Efficacy and Health. In: Liamputtong P, editor. *Handbook of Concepts in Health, Health Behavior and Environmental Health*. Singapore: Springer Nature Singapore; 2024. pp. 1–26. Available from: https://link.springer.com/10.1007/978-981-97-0821-5_15-1. Cited 2025 Dec 2.
- Bandura A. From thought to Action - Mechanisms of personal agency. *N Z J Psychol*. 1986;15(1):1–17.
- Bandura A. Self-efficacy: the exercise of control. New York: W.H. Freeman; 1997. p. 604.
- Bandura A. Self-efficacy: toward a unifying theory of behavioral change. *Psychol Rev*. 1977;84(2):191–215.
- Yesilyurt E, Ulas AH, Akan D. Teacher self-efficacy, academic self-efficacy, and computer self-efficacy as predictors of attitude toward applying computer-supported education. *Comput Hum Behav*. 2016;64:591–601.
- Peura P, Aro T, Raikonen E, Viholainen H, Koponen T, Usher EL, et al. Trajectories of change in reading self-efficacy: a longitudinal analysis of self-efficacy and its sources. *Contemp Educ Psychol*. 2021;64:101947.
- Rajani NB, Mastellos N, Filippidis FT. Self-Efficacy and motivation to quit of smokers seeking to quit: quantitative assessment of smoking cessation mobile apps. *JMIR MHEALTH UHEALTH*. 2021;9(4):e25030.
- Alvarez-Huerta P, Muela A, Larrea I. Entrepreneurial self-efficacy among first-year undergraduates: Gender, creative self-efficacy, leadership self-efficacy, and field of study. *Entrep Bus Econ Rev*. 2022;10(4):73–89.
- Ruggieri S, Gagliano M, Bonfanti RC, Cucinella N, Ingoglia S. Interaction through social media: development and validation of a social network site self-efficacy scale (SNS-SES). *Acta Psychol (Amst)*. 2023;235:103889.
- Schwarzer R, editor. *Self-efficacy: thought control of action*. London: Routledge, Taylor and Francis; 2014.
- Di W, Nie Y, Chua BL, Chye S, Teo T. Developing a Single-Item general Self-Efficacy scale: an initial study. *J Psychoeduc Assess*. 2023;41(5):583–98.
- Engel GL. The need for a new medical model: a challenge for biomedicine. *Science*. 1977;196(4286):129–36.
- Aune T, Juul EML, Beidel DC, Nordahl HM, Dvorak RD. Mitigating adolescent social anxiety symptoms: the effects of social support and social self-efficacy in findings from the Young-HUNT 3 study. *Eur Child Adolesc Psychiatry*. 2021;30(3):441–9.
- Boehnlein J, Altegoer L, Muck NK, Roesmann K, Redlich R, Dannlowski U, et al. Factors influencing the success of exposure therapy for specific phobia: a systematic review. *Neurosci Biobehav Rev*. 2020;108:796–820.
- Paersch C, Recher D, Schulz A, Henninger M, Schlup B, Künzler F, et al. Self-Efficacy effects on symptom experiences in daily life and early treatment success in anxiety patients. *Clin Psychol Sci J Assoc Psychol Sci*. 2025;13(1):178–94.
- Guzman Villegas-Frei M, Jubin J, Bucher CO, Bachmann AO. Self-efficacy, mindfulness, and perceived social support as resources to maintain the mental health of students in Switzerland's universities of applied sciences: a cross-sectional study. *BMC Public Health*. 2024;24(1):335.
- Muris P. Relationships between self-efficacy and symptoms of anxiety disorders and depression in a normal adolescent sample. *Personal Individ Differ*. 2002;32(2):337–48.
- Sharma PK, Kumra R. Relationship between mindfulness, depression, anxiety and stress: mediating role of self-efficacy. *Personal Individ Differ*. 2022;186:111363.
- Delahajj R, Van Dam K. Coping with acute stress in the military: the influence of coping style, coping self-efficacy and appraisal emotions. *Personal Individ Differ*. 2017;119:13–8.

38. Lipp A, Zhang XC, Dere E, Zlomuzica A. The role of self-efficacy in specific fears. *PLoS ONE*. 2023;18(3):e0283660.
39. Chacon L, Santoyo-Olsson J, Samayoa C, Alhomsí A, Stewart AL, Ortiz C, et al. Self-efficacy for coping with breast cancer treatment among Spanish-speaking Latinas. *Health Equity*. 2021;5(1):245–52.
40. Ozkaraman A, Kazak A, Dudakli N, Ozen H. Evaluation of the effect of self-efficacy on symptoms in gastrointestinal cancer patients. *J Palliat Care*. 2023;38(2):207–14.
41. Karademas EC, Roziner I, Mazzocco K, Pat-Horenczyk R, Sousa B, Oliveira-Maia AJ, et al. The mutual determination of self-efficacy to cope with cancer and cancer-related coping over time: a prospective study in women with breast cancer. *Psychol Health*. 2023;38(12):1635–48.
42. Lin PY, Lee TY, Liu CY, Lee YJ. The effect of self-efficacy in self-management on diabetes distress in young people with type 2 diabetes. *Healthcare*. 2021;9(12):1736.
43. Kara S. General self-efficacy and hypertension treatment adherence in Algerian private clinical settings. *J Public Health Afr*. 2022;13(3). Available from: <https://www.publichealthinfrica.org/jphia/article/view/2121>. Cited 2024 Feb 28.
44. Melgarejo Gonzalez-Conde V, Perez-Fernandez V, Ruiz-Esteban C, Valverde-Molina J. Impact of self-efficacy on the quality of life of children with asthma and their caregivers. *Arch Bronconeumol*. 2019;55(4):189–94.
45. Montalbano L, Ferrante G, Alesi M, La Grutta S. Integrating self-efficacy in the cyclical process of paediatric asthma management: a new perspective. *Psychol Health Med*. 2023;3(6):1582–90.
46. World Health Organization. World health statistics 2023: monitoring health for the SDGs. Geneva: World Health Organization; 2023. Available from: <https://www.who.int/news/item/19-05-2023-urgent-action-needed-to-tackle-stalled-progress-on-health-related-sustainable-development-goals>.
47. Barbosa JMA, Ribeiro CCC, Batista RFL, Brondani MA, Simões VMF, Bettiol H, et al. Behavioral risk factors for noncommunicable diseases associated with depression and suicide risk in adolescence. *Cad Saúde Pública*. 2022;38:e00055621.
48. Dhimal M, Chirico F, Bista B, Sharma S, Chalise B, Dhimal ML, et al. Impact of air pollution on global burden of disease in 2019. *Processes*. 2021;9(10):1719.
49. Yan M, Hou F, Xu J, Liu H, Liu H, Zhang Y, et al. The impact of prolonged exposure to air pollution on the incidence of chronic non-communicable disease based on a cohort in Tianjin. *Environ Res*. 2022;215:114251.
50. Vandenberghe D, Albrecht J. The financial burden of non-communicable diseases in the European union: a systematic review. *Eur J Public Health*. 2020;30(4):833–9.
51. Akseer N, Mehta S, Wigle J, Chera R, Brickman ZJ, Al-Gashm S, et al. Non-communicable diseases among adolescents: current status, determinants, interventions and policies. *BMC Public Health*. 2020;20(1):1908.
52. Kelishadi R. Life-Cycle Approach for Prevention of Non Communicable Disease. In: Kelishadi R, editor. *Primordial Prevention of Non Communicable Disease*. Cham: Springer International Publishing; 2019. pp. 1–6. (Advances in Experimental Medicine and Biology; vol. 1121). Available from: http://link.springer.com/10.1007/978-3-030-10616-4_1. Cited 2023 Oct 24.
53. Olatona FA, Onabanjo OO, Ugbaja RN, Nnoaham KE, Adelekan DA. Dietary habits and metabolic risk factors for non-communicable diseases in a university undergraduate population. *J Health Popul Nutr*. 2018;37(1):21.
54. Uddin R, Lee EY, Khan SR, Tremblay MS, Khan A. Clustering of lifestyle risk factors for non-communicable diseases in 304,779 adolescents from 89 countries: a global perspective. *Prev Med*. 2020;131:105955.
55. Gupta R, Xavier D. Hypertension. The most important Non communicable disease risk factor in India. *Indian Heart J*. 2018;70(4):565–72.
56. Cleveland Clinic. Huntington's Disease. 2023. Huntington's Disease: What Is It? Available from: <https://my.clevelandclinic.org/health/diseases/14369-huntingtons-disease>. Cited 2023 Nov 18.
57. National Cancer Institute. The Genetics of Cancer. 2022. The Genetics of Cancer - NCI. Available from: <https://www.cancer.gov/about-cancer/causes-prevention/genetics>. Cited 2023 Nov 18.
58. NHS. Inherited heart conditions. NHS inform. 2023. Available from: <https://www.nhsinform.scot/illnesses-and-conditions/heart-and-blood-vessels/conditions/inherited-heart-conditions/>. Cited 2023 Nov 18.
59. Chua RXY, Tay MJY, Ooi DSQ, Siah KTH, Tham EH, Shek LPC, et al. Understanding the link between allergy and neurodevelopmental disorders: a current review of factors and mechanisms. *Front Neurol*. 2021;11:603571.
60. Dawoodi S, Dawoodi I, Dixit P. Gastrointestinal problem among Indian adults: evidence from longitudinal aging study in India 2017-18. *Front Public Health*. 2022;10:911354.
61. Hepat A, Chakole S, Rannaware A. Psychological well-being of adult psoriasis patients: a narrative review. *Cureus J Med Sci*. 2023;15(4). Available from: <http://www.cureus.com/articles/138626-psychological-well-being-of-adult-psoriasis-patients-a-narrative-review>. Cited 2023 Nov 18.
62. Xia D, Han X, Zeng Y, Wang J, Xu K, Zhang T, et al. Disease trajectory of high neuroticism and the relevance to psychiatric disorders: a retro-prospective cohort study. *Acta Psychiatr Scand*. 2024;149(2):133–46.
63. Schwarzer R, Jerusalem M, Weinman J, Wright S, Johnston M. Generalized self-efficacy scale. *Meas Health Psychol Users Portf Causal Control Beliefs Windsor*. 1995.
64. Hodačová L, Cígler H, Vachková E, Mareš J. Psychometrické Vlastnosti české Verze Dotazníku obecné self-efficacy u populace hospitalizovaných pacientů. *Českoslov Psychol*. 2020;64(6):639–55.
65. d'Huaut D, Seker S, Bürgin D, Birkhölzer M, Boonmann C, Schmid M, et al. The stability of personality disorders and personality disorder criteria: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Clin Psychol Rev*. 2023;102:102284.
66. Barrantes-Vidal N, Kwapil TR. Predictive validity of psychometrically assessed schizotypy for psychopathology dimensions and functioning in an 8-Year multiwave study. *Schizophr Bull*. 2025;51(Suppl 2):S115–25.
67. Lenzenweger MF. Schizotypy 17 years on: prediction of schizotypic individual differences in midlife. *J Psychopathol Clin Sci*. 2025;134(4):438–47.
68. Kendler KS, Ohlsson H, Sundquist J, Sundquist K. The genetic epidemiology of schizotypal personality disorder. *Psychol Med*. 2024;54(9):2144–51.
69. Francois Z, Torrico TJ. Schizotypal Personality Disorder. In: *StatPearls*. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing; 2025. Available from: <http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK603720/>. Cited 2025 Dec 2.
70. Novák L, GitLab. 2021. Psychtoolbox: tools for psychology and psychometrics. R package version 0.0.1. Available from: <https://gitlab.com/lukas.novak/psychtoolbox>. Cited 2024 Oct 28.
71. Petersen MW, Carstensen TBW, Frostholm L, Wellnitz KB, Ørnbøl E, Jørgensen T, et al. High perceived stress and low Self-Efficacy are associated with functional somatic disorders: the DanFunD study. *Clin Epidemiol*. 2023;15:407–19.
72. Wojcek RK, Silva SG, Bailey DEJ, Knisely MR, Kwakkenbos L, Carrier ME, et al. Pain and self-efficacy among patients with systemic sclerosis: a scleroderma patient-centered intervention network cohort study. *Nurs Res*. 2021;70(5):334.
73. Tsuji H, Tetsunaga T, Tetsunaga T, Nishida K, Misawa H, Ozaki T. The factors driving self-efficacy in intractable chronic pain patients: a retrospective study. *J Orthop Surg*. 2019;14(1):473.
74. Lethem J, Slade PD, Troup JDG, Bentley G. Outline of a fear-avoidance model of exaggerated pain perception—I. *Behav Res Ther*. 1983;21(4):401–8.
75. Vlaeyen JWS, Crombez G, Linton SJ. The fear-avoidance model of pain. *Pain*. 2016;157(8):1588.
76. Vlaeyen JWS, Linton SJ. Fear-avoidance and its consequences in chronic musculoskeletal pain: a state of the Art. *Pain*. 2000;85(3):317.
77. Alemdar DK, Yilmaz G, Gunaydin N. The spiritual and religious coping of mothers with disabled children in Turkey: correlation between stress coping styles and self-efficacy. *J Relig Health*. 2023;62(2):888–905.
78. Freire C, Ferradas M, del Regueiro M, Rodriguez B, Valle S, Nunez A. Coping strategies and self-efficacy in university students: a person-centered approach. *Front Psychol*. 2020;11:841.
79. Agbaria Q, Abu Mokh A. Self-efficacy and optimism as predictors of coping with stress as assessed during the coronavirus outbreak. *Cogent Educ*. 2022;9(1):2080032.
80. Zahed K, Markert C, Sasangohar F. Understanding the role of beliefs on intentions and actual usage of a tool for self-management of mental health among college students. *Appl Ergon*. 2025;126:104485.
81. Bach M, Simhandl C. Chronic pain—a psychosomatic perspective. *Man Med*. 2020;58(1–2):27–33.
82. Stackeová D, Google D. 2021. Psychosomatika a zdravý životní styl.pdf. Available from: https://drive.google.com/file/d/1rA7fTSLGf4FpEDcPg9WtCpUJZRLOGeA3/view?usp=embed_facebook. Cited 2024 Feb 26.
83. Plaza-Gonzalez S, Zabala-Banos M, del Astasio-Picado C, Jurado-Palomo A. Psychological and sociocultural determinants in childhood asthma disease: impact on quality of life. *Int J Environ Res Public Health*. 2022;19(5):2652.
84. Tseng TJ, Wu CJ (Jo), Chang AM, editors. Theoretical asthma self-management program for Taiwanese adolescents with self-efficacy, outcome-expectancy, health behaviour, and asthma symptoms: a randomized controlled trial. *Contemp Clin Trials Commun*. 2020;19:100624.
85. Urun J, Muslu GK, Ozceker D. An explanation of the relationship between the attitudes of adolescents with asthma toward their illness and their self-efficacy. *Curr Psychol*. 2024;43(12):11373–82.

86. Mertsch P, Goetschke J, Walter J, Muemmler C, Ghiani A, Schuermann U, et al. Response to high-altitude triggers in seasonal asthmatics on and off inhaled corticosteroid treatment. *World Allergy Organ J*. 2022;15(10):100698.
87. Ora J, De Marco P, Gabriele M, Cazzola M, Rogliani P. Exercise-Induced asthma: managing respiratory issues in athletes. *J Funct Morphol Kinesiol*. 2024;9(1):15.
88. Price OJ, Simpson AJ. Exercise and asthma-trigger or treatment?. *Respir Med*. 2023;213:107247.
89. Brasier AR, Jarjour NN, editors. Precision approaches to heterogeneity in asthma. Cham: Springer International Publishing; 2023. (Advances in Experimental Medicine and Biology; vol. 1426). Available from: <https://link.springer.com/10.1007/978-3-031-32259-4>. Cited 2024 May 16.
90. Lewis KM, Matsumoto C, Cardinale E, Jones EL, Gold AL, Stringaris A, et al. Self-efficacy as a target for neuroscience research on moderators of treatment outcomes in pediatric anxiety. *J Child Adolesc Psychopharmacol*. 2020;30(4):205–14.
91. Monroy F, Astorga A, Ossandon M, Ramos C, Rodriguez C. Relationship between and self-efficacy and anxiety in college students in the Coquimbo region. *Eureka-Rev Cient Psicol*. 2023;20(2):313–27.
92. Uke T, Gawai J, Kasturkar P. Assess the relationship between personality traits (neuroticism, extraversion and self-efficacy) with anxiety and depression among aging population. *J Pharm Res Int*. 2021;33(45B):112–9.
93. Barcaccia B, Hartstone JM, Pallini S, Petrocchi N, Salianni AM, Medvedev ON. Mindfulness social safeness and self-reassurance as protective factors and self-criticism and revenge as risk factors for depression and anxiety symptoms in youth. *Mindfulness*. 2022;13(3):674–84.
94. Dagnino P, Ugarte MJ, Morales F, González S, Saralegui D, Ehrenthal JC. Risk factors for adult depression: adverse childhood experiences and personality functioning. *Front Psychol*. 2020;11. Available from: <https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/psychology/articles/10.3389/fpsyg.2020.594698>. Cited 2024 Feb 25.
95. Gossage L, Narayanan A, Dipnall JF, Iusitini L, Sumich A, Berk M, et al. Risk factors for depression in Pacific adolescents in New Zealand: a network analysis. *J Affect Disord*. 2022;311:373–82.
96. Narmandakh A, Roest AM, de Jonge P, Oldehinkel AJ. Psychosocial and biological risk factors of anxiety disorders in adolescents: a TRAILS report. *Eur Child Adolesc Psychiatry*. 2021;30(12):1969–82.
97. Remmerswaal KCP, ten Have M, de Graaf R, van Balkom AJLM, Penninx BWJH, Batelaan NM. Risk factors of chronic course of anxiety and depressive disorders: a 3-year longitudinal study in the general population. *Soc Psychiatry Epidemiol*. 2023. Available from: <https://www.webofscience.com/api/gateway?GWVersion=2&SrcAuth=DOI&SrcApp=WOS&KeyAID=10.1007%2F0127-023-02591-0&DestApp=DOI&SrcAppSID=EUW1ED0E20bU2wgnjrjwGw aHLv454&SrcTitle=SOCIAL+PSYCHIATRY+AND+PSYCHIATRIC+EPIDEMIOLOGY&DestDOIRegistrantName=Springer-Verlag>. Cited 2024 Feb 11.
98. Bakouni H, Ouimet MC, Desjardins S, Forget H, Vasiliadis HM. Childhood abuse/neglect and temporal patterns in late-life anxiety. *Aging Ment Health*. 2023;27(5):973–82.
99. Colak M, Sireli O, Dayi A. Adult separation anxiety and childhood trauma: the mediating role of cognitive distortions. *J Child Adolesc Trauma*. 2023;16(4):973–80.
100. Santomauro DF, Mantilla Herrera AM, Shadid J, Zheng P, Ashbaugh C, Pigott DM, et al. Global prevalence and burden of depressive and anxiety disorders in 204 countries and territories in 2020 due to the COVID-19 pandemic. *Lancet*. 2021;398(10312):1700–12.
101. Shojaati A, Kalantari M, Mulavi H. Do emotional abuse and personality traits predict early maladaptive schemas and social anxiety. *Early Child Dev Care*. 2021;191(3):389–402.
102. Taquet M, Holmes EA, Harrison PJ. Depression and anxiety disorders during the COVID-19 pandemic: knowns and unknowns. *Lancet*. 2021;398(10312):1665–6.
103. Hungnes T, Bachmann KE, Bjerke AH. Developing self-efficacy through an extra preparatory school year: lower secondary students' perspectives on teacher support. *Front Educ*. 2022;7:952854.
104. Sedillo-Hamann D. Building adolescent self-efficacy and resilience through social action. *Child Adolesc Soc Work J*. 2023;40(3):409–17.
105. Sticca F, Wustmann Seiler C, Gasser-Haas O. Familial risk factors and emotional problems in early childhood: the promotive and protective role of children's self-efficacy and self-concept. *Front Psychol*. 2020;11:547368.
106. Galindo-Dominguez H, Bezanilla MJ. The importance of personality and self-efficacy for stress management in higher education. *Int J Educ Psychol*. 2021;10(3):247–70.
107. Wang J, Liu D, Li G, Zhu J, Yue S, Li X, et al. The impact of self-efficacy on first onset and prognosis of major depressive disorder: findings from a longitudinal study in a sample of Chinese first-year university students. *Psychol Med*. 2022;52(1):178–83.
108. Svensén S, Bolstad I, Skomakerstuen Ødbehr L, Larsson G. Perceptions of self-efficacy, everyday stress, and symptoms of anxiety and depression among traumatized women in comprehensive treatment. *Eur J Psychotraumatology*. 2025;16(1):2582354.
109. Fürtjes S, Voss C, Rückert F, Peschel SKV, Kische H, Ollmann TM, et al. Self-efficacy, stress, and symptoms of depression and anxiety in adolescents: an epidemiological cohort study with ecological momentary assessment. *J Mood Anxiety Disord*. 2023;4:100039.
110. Bahar A. Determining the relationship between the level of self-efficacy and quality of life on coping with depression. *J Educ Res Nurs*. 2023;20(3):255–60.
111. Edmond SL, Werneke MW, Grigsby D, Young M, Harris G. The association between self-efficacy on function and pain outcomes among patients with chronic low back pain managed using the McKenzie approach: a prospective cohort study. *J Man Manip Ther*. 2023;31(1):38–45.
112. de la Gonzalez A, Perez de Sevilla GG, Domingez Balmaseda D, Martin Vera D, Montero Martinez M, Del Blanco Muniz JA. Relationship between self-efficacy and headache impact, anxiety, and physical activity levels in patients with chronic tension-type headache: an observational study. *Behav Neurol*. 2022;6:20228387249.
113. Katzenberger B, Fuchs S, Schwettmann L, Strobl R, Hauser A, Koller D, et al. Association of self-efficacy, risk attitudes, and time preferences with functioning in older patients with vertigo, dizziness, and balance disorders in a tertiary care setting—results from the MobilE-TRA2 cohort. *Front Neurol*. 2023;14:1316081.
114. Ghose SM, Dzierzewski JM, Dautovich ND. Sleep and self-efficacy: the role of domain specificity in predicting sleep health. *Sleep Health*. 2023;9(2):190–5.
115. Dimov S, Mundy LK, Bayer JK, Jacka FN, Canterford L, Patton GC. Diet quality and mental health problems in late childhood. *Nutr Neurosci*. 2021;24(1):62–70.
116. Kenardy J, Brown WJ, Vogt E. Dieting and health in young Australian women. *Eur Eat Disord Rev*. 2001;9(4):242–54.
117. Okechukwu CE. Effect of aerobic exercise on some parameters of cardiovascular health among male problem gamblers. *Int Arch Health Sci*. 2019;6(4):115–21.
118. Son E, Kwon KH. Dance/exercise impact for adults with mental health disorders: a systematic review. *Body Mov Dance Psychother*. 2024. Available from: <https://www.webofscience.com/api/gateway?GWVersion=2&SrcAuth=Dyna micDOI&Article&SrcApp=WOS&KeyAID=10.1080%2F17432979.2024.2308625&DestApp=DOI&SrcAppSID=EUW1ED0F2FqU4arHobQrogzNSfmsq&SrcTitle=BODY+MOVEMENT+AND+DANCE+IN+PSYCHOTHERAPY&DestDOIRegistrant Name=Informa+UK+%28Taylor+%26+Francis%29>. Cited 2024 Apr 9.
119. Haight BL, Peddie L, Crosswell AD, Hives BA, Almeida DM, Puterman E. Combined effects of cumulative stress and daily stressors on daily health. *Health Psychol*. 2023;42(5):325–34.
120. Nielsen SS, Skou ST, Larsen AE, Sondergaard J, Christensen JR. Associations of health-related quality of life with sociodemographic characteristics, health, pain, and lifestyle factors, and motivation for changing lifestyle in adults living with chronic pain: a cross-sectional exploratory study. *Scand J Pain*. 2022;22(1):142–53.
121. Al-Ghanim L, Alkazemi D. Factors associated with self-efficacy toward healthy eating and physical activity among Kuwaiti adolescent girls. *Curr Res Nutr FOOD Sci*. 2021;9(3):890–903.
122. Bouwman EP, Onwezen MC, Taufik D, de Buissonje D, Ronteltap A. Brief self-efficacy interventions to increase healthy dietary behaviours: evidence from two randomized controlled trials. *Br FOOD J*. 2020;122(11):3297–311.
123. Dzerounian J, Pirrie M, AlShenaiber L, Angeles R, Marzanek F, Agarwal G. Health knowledge and self-efficacy to make health behaviour changes: a survey of older adults living in Ontario social housing. *BMC Geriatr*. 2022;22(1):473.
124. Efthymiou V, Charmandari E, Vlachakis D, Tsitsika A, Palasz A, Chrousos G, et al. Adolescent self-efficacy for diet and exercise following a school-based multicomponent lifestyle intervention. *Nutrients*. 2022;14(1):97.
125. Andretta JR, McKay MT. Self-efficacy and well-being in adolescents: a comparative study using variable and person-centered analyses. *Child Youth Serv Rev*. 2020;118:105374.
126. Ballantyne JC, Sullivan MD. Is chronic pain a disease? *J Pain*. 2022;23(10):1651–65.

127. Liu X, Li Y, Cao X. Bidirectional reduction effects of perceived stress and general self-efficacy among college students: a cross-lagged study. *Humanit Soc Sci Commun*. 2024;11(1):271.
128. Sethi A, Imran D, Student. The influence of perceived stress on self-efficacy and life satisfaction in young adults. *Int J Res Anal Rev*. 2025;30:11:316.
129. Nouri-Majd S, Salari-Moghaddam A, Keshteli AH, Afshar H, Esmailzadeh A, Adibi P. Coffee and caffeine intake in relation to symptoms of psychological disorders among adults. *Public Health Nutr*. 2022;25(12):3509–19.
130. Lofffield E, Cornelis MC, Caporaso N, Yu K, Sinha R, Freedman N. Association of coffee drinking with mortality by genetic variation in caffeine metabolism: findings from the UK biobank. *JAMA Intern Med*. 2018;178(8):1086–97.
131. Emadi RC, Kamangar F. Coffee's impact on health and well-being. *Nutrients*. 2025;17(15):2558.
132. Wang X, Ma H, Sun Q, Li J, Heianza Y, Van Dam RM, et al. Coffee drinking timing and mortality in US adults. *Eur Heart J*. 2025;46(8):749–59.
133. Naidoo-Chetty M, du Plessis M. Systematic review of the job demands and resources of academic staff within higher education institutions. *Int J High Educ*. 2021;10:268.
134. Czarniecka-Skubina E, Pielak M, Salek P, Korzeniowska-Ginter R, Owczarek T. Consumer choices and habits related to coffee consumption by Poles. *Int J Environ Res Public Health*. 2021;18(8):3948.
135. Patel DS, Rawal Y, Patani P. Effects of caffeine on human body. *J Pharm Negat Results*. 2022;13(Special Issue 8):2087–92.

Publisher's note

Springer Nature remains neutral with regard to jurisdictional claims in published maps and institutional affiliations.